

Deep Neural Networks for Transmission Impairment Mitigation in Long-Reach 5G Access Networks

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Abstract—The mitigation of transmission impairments in optical communication systems requires implementation of digital signal processing that can easily adapt to changing conditions and work on continual streams of data. In this paper, the application of continual learning in deep neural networks for transmission impairments in long haul transmission systems is considered. This work investigates the novel use of continual learning to overcome the problem of catastrophic forgetting and remembrance in deep neural networks that can be used for dispersion and nonlinearity mitigation in long-haul transmission systems. We perform comparisons between state-of-the-art methods such as iCaRL, DGR, EWC, XdG and traditional DNNs implementations typically used in optical networks. We demonstrate improvements in training accuracy towards signal recovery, and increased flexibility for DNN equalization applications. The results show that the method can be successfully used for fiber lengths ranging from less than 1km to 250km and over with no need to retrain the network from scratch for each fibre length. The introduction of continual learning enables training DNNs on a continuous stream of data with no loss of prior knowledge.

Keywords—Deep Learning, Long-Reach 5G Access Networks, Continual Learning, Optical Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

A broad range of machine learning equalization techniques have been considered in wireless systems. Only recently, however, they have been applied to fiber optics transmission systems that are critical in efforts to deliver low latency, high bandwidth and high dynamic range to highly densified 5G and beyond networks over long reach fiber spans [1]. Through implicit training, these techniques learn a mapping from a baseband signal onto a space determined by the distribution of a known training sequence. They combine the nonlinear equalization functionality with optimum symbol classification. This implies that instead of using hard decision boundaries they can adapt based on the residual nonlinear distortion that occurs in the signal [2]. An alternative approach considers the challenge of reconstructing the signal as a regression problem. The algorithm learns the inverse transfer function of the nonlinear link. This approach offers powerful statistical signal processing capabilities for dealing with nonlinear transmission effects. Recent advances in Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) have been coupled with the increasing processing power and miniaturization of

semiconductors to enable development of advanced digital signal processing solutions [3].

DNNs are designed to solve classification and/or regression problems [15]. DNNs are used as the base for developing intelligent solutions in a wide spectrum of application areas [16][17]. In the case of supervised learning, this is performed with the help of a training set. The only way to add new information is to include new data samples. The DNNs create a static model that requires re-training each time new information needs to be added. This implies that DNNs can be very efficient on a specific problem that is fixed in a specific time. They lack, however, the capability of adapting to new tasks without losing some/or the entirety of the knowledge previously acquired. To address this challenge, it is a common practice to keep all the previous data samples and add new training data each time there is a need. This practice quickly becomes intractable especially for long data streams and leads to a number of problems such as lack of data storage, long processing times and computational limitations [4]. These problems are relevant in the context of digital signal processing where a stream of data is used for the training. Continual Learning (CL) is a new approach to the problem of learning from an infinite stream of data that can gradually extend acquired knowledge with no need to retain the data samples used previously in the training process [5]. Its main objective is to address two main problems: catastrophic forgetting, the performance degradation on previous tasks; and catastrophic remembering, the worsening ability to discriminate between data from different tasks [4]. In this paper, we introduce CL and integrate it with common DNN architectures used for impairment mitigation in long-haul transmission systems. The main objective of this work is to validate and compare the available methods of CL and provide a proof of concept for a novel approach in the context of long reach access networks. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the use of DNNs in the context of fiber transmission systems. Section 3 introduces the concepts of CL and discusses available methods. Section 4 outlines the setup of our experiments. Section 5 presents the results. Conclusions and future work are discussed in Section 6.

II. DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS IN FIBER TRANSMISSION SYSTEMS

ML techniques are mainly applied in the physical layer as an efficient tool to mitigate (non-)linear effects in optical

fibers. They outperform inaccurate analytical models that are too simple to model the effects of self-phase modulation (SPM), cross-phase modulation (XPM), Chromatic Dispersion (CD) and its cooperation with transmitter phase noise, Polarization Mode Dispersion (PMD), and inter-symbol interference stemming from the transmitter bandwidth limitation [6]. These effects may cause prohibitive levels of signal distortion at the receiver and considerably degrade its sensitivity. Supervised ML models can be designed in such a way to directly capture and model these effects. This is done by using historical data and learning the input-output relations between the monitored parameters and the desired outputs. In general, optical communication systems can be considered non-linear channels with memory. The memory can be defined as a function of chromatic dispersion and the Kerr effect. A typical optical signal can be described as a function of time t using the following relationship:

$$A(z = 0, t) = \sum_k a_k f(t - kT) \quad (1)$$

where a_k represents transmitted symbols, k timeslots, $f(t)$ is a waveform function of a carrier pulse and T is a symbol interval. This function can be further transformed into a discrete representation of the signal and form a series of vectors $\xi_k = (\xi_k^1, \dots, \xi_k^n)$ with a fixed number of n elements, forming an infinite set $\{\xi_k^j\}$ of regularly spaced signal samples where n/T is the sampling rate. The signal at the receiver can be similarly represented as a set of vectors $\eta_k = (\eta_k^1, \dots, \eta_k^n)$. A fixed set of input signals has an impact on the output signal. This representation of data constitutes a very good fit for NNs that accept an input vector $vi_k = (vi_k^1, \dots, vi_k^n)$ with fixed number of elements and produce an output vector $vo_k = (vo_k^1, \dots, vo_k^n)$ with fixed n number of elements. A common architecture used in fiber nonlinearity mitigation is fully-connected feed-forward neural networks. In these networks, the neurons in consecutive layers are connected to each other in a fully connected fashion. Each neuron has an associated weight that is updated to reduce the network error at each gradient descent step. These networks do not make any assumption on the characteristics of the data that is being modelled. It is therefore expensive in terms of memory and computation [7].

Several studies showcased the potential of deep learning to deal with the nonlinearities occurring in fiber optic systems. Catanese et al. presented a fully connected network to deal with the nonlinear effects in the fiber link. This network was utilized to determine the inverse transfer function of the transmission channel. The experimental results over a simulated channel (200 Gbps DP-16-QAM) showed that the network improved the bit error rate significantly compared to linear equalization [8]. Koike-Akine et al. presented a DL-based turbo equalization method which was able to cope with nonlinear fiber impairments for coherent optical communications. The researchers relied on deep residual networks and considerably accelerated decoding convergence resulting in a gain in achievable throughput (0.61 b/s/Hz) [9]. Yi et al. suggested a CNN-based equalization technique. The researchers conducted experiments to test the performance of the technique for 56Gb/s PAM4 and 100Gb/s PAM8/PAM16 transmissions. From their experiments it was concluded that recurrent neural network are suitable candidates for sequence signals [10].

Current DNNs used in Communication systems can achieve high impairment distortion cancellation when trained on fixed fiber lengths [6]. Learning how to perform well on multiple tasks for dynamically changing base conditions, e.g. varying fiber lengths, still remains challenging. Standard NN trained on a new task tend to result in sub-optimal parameter configuration and “forget” the knowledge acquired from the previous task. There have been several attempts to alleviate this problem. These methods fall into the category of CL and further into one of two sub-categories: single-headed or multi-headed [11]. The single-headed methods do not require task identity to be known, while for the multi-headed methods the task identity has to be known a priori. They are both closely related to the type of the neural network architecture used and to the layout of the output layer. The single-headed implementations use the same output layer for every task as distinct from multi-headed implementations that use a separate output layer for each task. This makes the single-headed methods more versatile and practical.

There have been a number of approaches to mitigate catastrophic forgetting in neural networks. The most natural and simplest approach is to explicitly define subnetworks for any given task. The common solutions are to either randomly assign a set of nodes in the network that will participate in each task, or use a more advanced method that will identify the most optimal set of nodes based on an optimization algorithm. The most widely used methods of optimization in the literature are evolutionary algorithms or gradient descent [12]. The optimization methods require information about the specific task the network is used for. In these solutions, different parts of the network are used in execution dependent on the specific task. The other approach to mitigate catastrophic forgetting is called regularized optimization. The method is most commonly used in single-headed CL where the task identity information is not available. It is similar to the previously discussed method in the sense that, during training, a different part of the network is used. Regularized optimization, however, uses the entire network for execution and does not need the additional task information identity. In the method of Elastic Weight Consolidation, this is achieved during training by using a regularization technique that imposes a constraint on the network's parameters. This process is performed separately for each new task. The method estimates the individual importance of the network parameters for a specific given task and applies a penalization factor for future changes to those parameters [13]. In practice, this means that the learning is adopted according to different parts of the network based on the significance of the parameters for a specific task. Another approach is to adopt a novel strategy for class-incremental learning with the use of data “exemplars”, as proposed in iCaRL [14]. In this case, the network parameters and a database of “exemplars” need to be stored. The method uses three components. First, the nearest-mean-of-exemplars classifier is a herding-based step for prioritized exemplar selection. Next, a representation learning step that uses “exemplars” with a special form of distillation for feature extraction. Its objective is to learn classifiers and a feature representation simultaneously from a data stream. Finally, to reduce the catastrophic forgetting, the method uses a replay strategy together with novel inputs.

The last set of methods used in the mitigation of catastrophic forgetting is based on modifying the training data. These methods rely on creating a complementary training

dataset that incorporates pseudo-data that represents the combined knowledge acquired in the previous tasks. There are three approaches. The first is to store the data from previous tasks. Second, to use a generative model that is capable of capturing the distribution of the input data from previous tasks or to use the current input, label it using the learned model from the previous task and use the output as a pseudo-data. The last method eliminates the need to learn a generative model and to store the data used previously with other tasks.

IV. ARCHITECTURE SETUP

In order to identify the most suitable CL method for impairment mitigation in long-haul transmission systems we have used one common DNN scenario. The network has been trained on a total number of 20 tasks. Each task is corresponding to a different fiber length $< 1, 10, \dots, 200$ km, considering standard single mode fiber (SMF), and an externally generated 10Gb/s signal using a fully random binary sequence. We have a DNN configuration of four fully connected layers. The output layer is a standard softmax layer. The activation function used for each layer is ReLU with the exception of the sigmoid output layer. We use ADAM stochastic gradient descent algorithm to perform parameter updates and MSE as a loss function. The learning rate was set to 0.001. All the models have been trained for 500 epochs. To ensure the comparison is consistent the same neural network architecture has been used for all the CL methods. Our dataset consisted of randomly generated symbols with input-output pairs. The dataset has been divided into test, training and validation with the following ratio 70% / 20% / 10%, respectively. For this study, we compare the following CL methods: iCaRL, DGR, EWC and XdG. In addition, we have also included two baseline models for performance comparison where no CL has been applied.

V. RESULTS

Initially, our evaluation has been conducted with the use of a 200km fixed size fibre length dataset. The fully connected network achieved 99.9987%. This result shows high impairment cancellation capabilities. The next set of results presented in the first column of table I compares the accuracy of reconstruction of the input signal at the receiver side for different SMF lengths $< 1, 20, \dots, 200$ km. The DNNs have been trained on a dataset of fixed 100 km length. Our results show a change in accuracy achieved for increasing fiber lengths, as the total accumulated dispersion increases. The table also shows that the equalizer accuracy reaches 100% for all the fibre lengths lower than that used for training. This would imply that the DNN can be trained on the longest possible fibre length to provide the best coverage for all the different fibre lengths. For the 200KM length case, we have trained the DNNs on the highest considered fibre length (200 km). The results that are included in the second column of Table I, show that training a DNN on a fixed fiber length is not enough to create a viable equalizer that would work equally well for all different fibre lengths. This means that in order to create a universal signal equalizer, the DNN has to be trained on all possible fibre lengths in incremental steps.

We next assess the overall accuracy when training the DNNs in incremental steps divided into tasks. First, the DNNs were trained and evaluated with a dataset considering the back-to-back scenario (0 km). Next, the parameters have been saved and used to initialize the weights of another DNN that was trained on the data for 10 km fibre transmission. This process was repeated up to the 200 km SMF length. The

results are presented in column 3 of Table I. The results show that the incremental approach suffers from the catastrophic forgetting problem. Next experiment evaluates the performance of the DNN signal equalizer when trained on the dataset of all fibre lengths. The main purpose of the study is to create a baseline for further investigation on the performance of the various CL methods. The results for this study are shown in column 4 of Table I. Our results show a considerable improvement in terms of accuracy for all the fiber lengths over the incremental approach. However, for most access network applications, training the DNNs on the entire dataset for all fiber lengths is an intractable problem and cannot be efficiently performed in a real-life context. The approach may only be feasible for a limited number of data samples and in a limited setup. One needs to adopt CL approaches, in order to train the DNN on a continuous stream of data and on multiple fibre lengths to avoid catastrophic forgetting.

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE OF NETWORK (100KM AND 200KM)

Fiber length (km)	Accuracy on corresponding fiber length for 100KM	Accuracy on corresponding fiber length for 200KM	Accuracy for incremental training	Training on dataset of all fibre lengths
0	100%	93.5492%	91.0531%	100.0000%
20	100%	92.5717%	93.0983%	100.0000%
40	100%	91.8143%	87.4893%	100.0000%
60	100%	88.3689%	82.2938%	100.0000%
80	100%	87.4891%	89.4746%	100.0000%
100	100%	91.9738%	83.9596%	100.0000%
120	99.828%	85.0700%	84.2840%	100.0000%
140	96.627%	88.8453%	94.1624%	99.9978%
160	85.302%	87.5748%	96.6096%	99.9988%
180	79.010%	95.8334%	98.2773%	99.9993%
200	76.346%	99.9987%	100.0000%	99.9963%
Mean	94.2830%	91.1899%	90.9729%	99.9993%

We next perform a comparison of different CL approaches in order to identify the most appropriate methods of CL for accumulated dispersion mitigation in long reach optical systems. Table II showcases the mean values for all considered fibre lengths $< 1, 10, \dots, 200$ km. Table II shows a clear spread in the accuracy results between the different CL methods, ranging from 91.3857% to 99.9587%. The results show that the XdG method is more successful than EWC in mitigating catastrophic forgetting. All the methods however have higher accuracy than the incremental baseline method with no CL used. The best accuracy has been achieved with the use of XdG method. This method, however, requires that a specific task information identifier is added to the input. This requirement is not preferable, especially when using CL, as it may affect the flexibility of the DNNs and their use. The next best result is achieved with the use of the DGR method. This method does not require an additional task information identifier and is our preference for the investigation in the following studies.

TABLE II. CL METHODS FOR FULLY-CONNECTED NEURAL NETWORKS TRAINED ON ALL TASKS (<1,10,....200KM)

Approach	Method	Mean Accuracy
Baseline	Incremental	90.9729%
Baseline	All dataset	99.9993%
Replay	iCaRL	97.5673%
Replay	DGR	98.1094%
Replay	DGR (Continuous)	100%
Regularization	EWC	91.3857%
Task-specific	XdG	99.9587%

The accuracy results for DGR are lower than the results of DNNs trained on the entire dataset for all the fibre lengths. This is understandable, as when the DNNs are properly trained on the entire dataset they cannot suffer from the problem of catastrophic forgetting. The main benefits of using CL, however, are twofold. Firstly, it enables learning from continuous streams of data, potentially increasing the accuracy/performance on a set of given tasks. Secondly, it allows flexibility and adaptation to new tasks without a loss of prior knowledge from the previous tasks. To quantify these benefits, we used the DNN models trained on all tasks as our base model (“All dataset”) and compared it with the performance of DGR. The DGR model has been trained using a continuous stream of data as opposed to a fixed dataset – as per the approach used in the last study. The mean accuracy for signal equalization improves from 98.1094% to 100% (accuracy given to the fourth most significant digit), achieving better results than the base models when trained with the use of CL. While the focus of the paper was to demonstrate the potential of CL to improve transmission impairment mitigation compared to standard deep learning approaches, it is important to highlight some of the advantages of the proposed approach as to the methods presented in section III. The proposed approach was able to overcome the problem of catastrophic forgetting and remembrance faced. It removed the need of retraining the network for each fiber length, and enabled training on a continuous stream of data with no loss of prior knowledge while maintaining a very high degree of accuracy.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper has presented an overview of DNN methods for accumulated impairment mitigation in long reach optical transmission systems with special considerations to the latest state of the art CL techniques. An introduction to CL and deep learning approaches for reach and power budget extension in optical networks has been performed in this work, outlining the advantages and motivations behind using our CL approach. A comparison study for the selected CL methods (iCaRL, DGR, EWC, XdG) has been conducted with the most commonly used DNNs for signal equalization. An improvement in accuracy can be achieved with the use of the DGR method when trained on a continuous stream of data. The introduction of CL to the already established DNN methods used in optical networking poses an important step forward towards long reach, high power budget data transmission. CL enables increased flexibility on multiple tasks with no loss in performance on already trained networks.

Future work will include experiments with other DNN architectures such as CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks), and focus on identifying the most optimal setup for continuous learning in the context of signal equalization for long-reach, high-capacity optical access, considering a number of additional CL methods.

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